

Algorithm for Detecting Brain Strokes Using Machine Learning Techniques

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ABSTRACT

The brain serves as the primary upper organ of the human body. A stroke is a medical condition characterized by the rupture of blood vessels in the brain, leading to brain damage. Symptoms can arise when the flow of blood and essential nutrients to the brain is disrupted. Stroke is classified as a medical emergency and can result in long-term neurological impairment, complications, and frequently, death. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), stroke ranks as the leading cause of death and disability globally. Timely recognition of various stroke warning signs can mitigate the severity of the event. This study aims to predict the likelihood of a brain stroke occurring at an early stage by employing deep learning and machine learning methodologies. A reliable dataset for stroke prediction was sourced from the Kaggle platform to evaluate the algorithm's effectiveness. Several classification models were utilized in this research, including Random Forest, Decision Tree, Logistic Regression, K Neighbors, SVM, and Naive Bayes. In this paper we proposed brain stroke detection using different machine learning algorithms with statistical and software approaches with accuracy. Also, compare the two methods and given best solution for brain stroke detection. Among the all machine learning classifiers, the Random Forest classifier achieved the highest classification accuracy at 99%.

KEYWORDS: Brain Stroke, Machine Learning Techniques, Deep Neural Network, SVM, ANN

1. INTRODUCTION

The various components of the human body and their functions are essential to sustaining life. Stroke is a

critical condition that can lead to death, particularly prevalent in individuals over the age of 65. Just as heart attacks impair cardiac function, strokes disrupt brain

activity. Strokes occur due to either a reduction in blood supply to the brain or the rupture of blood vessels within the brain. When a blockage or rupture occurs, the brain's tissues are deprived of necessary blood and oxygen. Currently, stroke ranks as the fifth leading cause of death in both developed and developing countries [1]. Timely medical intervention significantly enhances the likelihood of a full recovery for stroke patients. It is crucial for anyone experiencing a stroke to seek immediate medical attention, as delays can result in death, irreversible disability, or brain damage. Various factors contribute to the risk of stroke, including diet, lack of physical activity, alcohol consumption, tobacco use, personal and family medical history, and other health complications, as noted by the National Heart, Lung, and Blood Institute [2].

Significant progress has been achieved in clinical and medical services through the application of artificial intelligence, machine learning, and data science methodologies. At the core of this advancement is machine learning, which is employed to identify potential issues at earlier stages. Stroke, a serious condition that can be effectively treated if detected early, is one of several diseases that can be prevented through timely prediction. In the healthcare industry, machine learning plays a vital role in both the diagnosis and prognosis of various illnesses. Currently, machine learning algorithms are utilized to forecast the incidence of strokes [3, 4]. The analysis of large volumes of medical data necessitates robust data analysis tools. A major focus of research in this domain is the integration of artificial intelligence (AI) within medical practices. By examining a patient's medical history, the system can identify individuals who are at a higher risk of developing certain conditions. This predictive capability is based on an analysis of various factors, including age, blood pressure, glucose levels, and more. When multiple variables are involved, classification algorithms are used to anticipate disease outcomes. Research has explored the use of a feed-forward multi-layer artificial neural network-based deep learning model for stroke prediction [5]. Additionally, similar studies have been conducted to create intelligent systems aimed at predicting strokes based on patient data [6, 7].

Previous research on strokes has primarily focused on forecasting heart attacks, with limited attention given to brain strokes. The primary objective of this paper is to

demonstrate the application of machine learning algorithms, boosting techniques, and artificial neural networks (ANN) in predicting the occurrence of brain strokes. A significant contribution of this study is the utilization of various algorithms on a publicly available dataset from the Kaggle website, allowing for a comparison to determine the most effective prediction method for stroke onset. In this investigation, neural networks and machine learning algorithms are employed as classification tools to predict the presence of stroke disease based on a range of associated characteristics. To reduce dimensionality, the principal component analysis (PCA) technique is applied, ensuring that only the most relevant features for stroke prediction are retained.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Previous research has explored various topics related to stroke prediction. Jeena et al. [3] examined multiple risk factors to assess the probability of stroke occurrence. They employed a regression-based approach to analyze the correlation between specific factors and their impact on stroke risk. Adam et al. [8] utilized decision tree methods and the k-nearest neighbor algorithm in their investigation to forecast stroke events. Their findings indicated that the decision tree method proved to be more effective for medical professionals in predicting stroke occurrences. Singh and Choudhary [9] leveraged the Cardiovascular Health Study (CHS) dataset to anticipate stroke in patients. Emon et al. [10] applied various machine learning classification algorithms, including XGBoost, Random Forest, Naive Bayes, Logistic Regression, and Decision Tree, on a dataset sourced from Kaggle. Kansadub et al. [11] explored stroke likelihood using decision trees, neural networks, and Naive Bayes analysis, focusing on predicting strokes from their data while assessing the accuracy and AUC of their model. Tazin et al. [12] aimed to facilitate early stroke prediction through the implementation of Logistic Regression (LR), Decision Tree (DT) Classification, Random Forest (RF) Classification, and a Voting Classifier.

Random Forest emerged as the most effective algorithm for this particular task. Chetan Sharma et al. [13] introduced a supervised algorithm, Random Forest, utilizing a dataset sourced from a publicly available repository to forecast the likelihood of a stroke occurring

in the near future. Additionally, a feed-forward multi-layer artificial neural network-based deep learning model aimed at stroke prediction was explored in [5]. Research focused on creating an intelligent system for stroke prediction using patient records was also conducted in [14]. Hung et al. [15] performed a comparative analysis of machine learning and deep learning models, developing stroke prediction models from an electronic medical claims database. Fang et al. [16] implemented three contemporary deep learning approaches (CNN, LSTM, ResNet) and compared their performance against various machine learning algorithms, including Deep Forest, Random Forest, and Support Vector Machine, in the context of clinical prediction. Mahesh et al. [12] evaluated the performance metrics of several deep learning algorithms, such as CNN, Densenet, and VGG16, to automate the prediction of brain strokes.

Using machine learning algorithms such as logistic regression, random forests naive bayes, multi-linear perception decision tree, support vector machine, and k-nearest neighbors to classify stroke patients and determine the most likely candidate for therapy [17].

This paper attempts to assess whether or not a system has been hacked by malicious malware by employing machine learning techniques such as support vector machines and principal component analysis. Various performance metrics, including accuracy, precision, recall, F1 score, and the AUC curve (under the ROC curve), are evaluated and compared among the classification models to ascertain which model provides the most accurate predictions on the dataset. Additionally, the experimental results of the proposed methods were juxtaposed with existing studies to highlight the novelty of this research.

3. METHODOLOGY

The present system employs data mining techniques that provide a comprehensive overview of information tracking from both semantic and syntactic viewpoints. The use of limited supervised learning models has resulted in low accuracy. To address this issue, we will implement boosting and bagging methods along with various models.

In the proposed system, we will utilize several machine learning algorithms, including Support Vector Machine, Random Forest, and Decision Tree. In this

proposed system to evaluate all these algorithms against one another to identify the model that achieves the highest accuracy. The best model for our dataset will be selected based on the accuracy score obtained.

The model undergoes training through various classification techniques following a data split. In this research, classification tasks were successfully executed utilizing Random Forest, Decision Tree, Logistic Regression, K Nearest Neighbors, SVM with a linear kernel, and Naive Bayes. The workflow is illustrated in the accompanying figure 1.

a) Data Set:

A data set refers to an organized collection of data. For tabular data, it typically aligns with one or more database tables, where each column signifies a specific variable and each row represents an individual record within the data set. This data set includes values for various variables, such as gender, age, and body mass index (BMI) of individuals. Additionally, data sets may comprise a series of documents or files. The dataset utilized for stroke prediction was employed in the study.

The dataset comprises 5,000 rows and 12 columns. The output column, labeled "stroke," contains binary values of either 1 or 0. A value of 0 signifies that no stroke risk has been identified, while a value of 1 indicates the presence of stroke risk. In this dataset, the occurrence of 0 in the stroke column is more prevalent than that of 1. Specifically, there are 289 rows with a value of 1, compared to 4768 rows with a value of 0. To enhance the accuracy of the analysis, data preprocessing techniques are employed to achieve a balanced dataset.

Figure 1. Work flow of the proposed methodology

b) Data Pre-Processing:

Data preprocessing is essential prior to model development, as it eliminates unnecessary noise and outliers from the dataset that could hinder the model's training process. This phase focuses on addressing any factors that may impede the model's efficiency. Once the relevant dataset is gathered, it must undergo cleaning and preparation for effective model construction. As previously mentioned, the dataset comprises twelve features. Initially, the column labeled 'id' is removed, as it does not contribute to the model's development. Subsequently, the dataset is examined for any null values, which are addressed accordingly. In this instance, the null values in the BMI column are filled using the mean of that specific data column.

c) Learning Algorithms:

1) Random Forest Classifier: Random forests can be utilized for both classification and regression tasks. However, their most common applications are found in classification problems. A forest with a higher number of individual trees tends to be more resilient on average than one with fewer trees. This approach, similar to the random forest technique, builds decision trees from data samples, gathers predictions from each tree, and then aggregates these predictions to identify the best option. By averaging the results, this ensemble method is more effective at minimizing overfitting compared to a single decision tree.

2) Naive Bayes Algorithm: Naive Bayes is a supervised learning method utilized in machine learning, grounded in the principles of the naïve theorem. This algorithm operates on the assumption that the presence of one feature does not influence the presence of another, meaning that the existence of one feature is independent of others. The foundation of this approach lies in Bayes' theorem, a mathematical principle of conditional probability that calculates the likelihood of an event occurring based on the assumption that a specific condition has been met. By applying Bayes' theorem, one can evaluate conditional probabilities, determining the probability of a particular event given that another event has already taken place.

3) Logistic Regression: Logistic regression is a classification algorithm in machine learning designed to estimate the likelihood of a categorical dependent variable. In this model, the dependent variable is binary, represented by values of 1 (indicating success or

affirmation) and 0 (indicating failure or negation). Essentially, logistic regression calculates the probability $P(Y=1)$ based on the input variable X .

4) K-Nearest Neighbor (KNN): K-Nearest Neighbor is a fundamental machine learning algorithm that operates on a supervised learning framework. The K-NN algorithm relies on the principle of similarity, categorizing new data points based on their resemblance to existing cases. It retains all available data and classifies incoming data points according to their similarity to these stored cases. Consequently, when new data is introduced, it can be efficiently categorized into the most appropriate class using the K-NN algorithm. While K-NN can be applied to both regression and classification tasks, it is predominantly utilized for classification purposes. During the training phase, the K-NN algorithm simply retains the dataset, and upon receiving new data, it assigns that data to the category that closely matches it.

5) Decision Tree (DT): DT classification addresses both regression and classification challenges. This method employs a supervised learning framework along with an output variable, exhibiting characteristics similar to a tree structure. The decision tree consists of two main elements: the decision node and the leaf node. Initially, the data is divided at the first node, and subsequently combined at the second node to produce the output. Because DT reflects the process a human follows when constructing a tangible object, it is easy to comprehend. The algorithm posits that the presence or absence of specific features in the dataset is interdependent, facilitating the categorization of the target into a specific class.

6) Support Vector Machine (SVM): SVM is a widely utilized algorithm in Supervised Learning, applicable to both Classification and Regression tasks. However, its primary application lies in addressing Classification challenges within Machine Learning. The main objective of the SVM algorithm is to establish an optimal line or decision boundary that divides n -dimensional space into distinct classes, facilitating the accurate categorization of new data points in the future. This optimal decision boundary is referred to as a hyperplane.

SVM identifies the extreme points or vectors that contribute to the formation of the hyperplane. These critical cases are known as support vectors, which is the reason the algorithm is named Support Vector Machine.

Steps for executing the Project:

1. Install the required packages
2. Load the datasets.
3. Pre-process the data.
4. Split the dataset into train and test.
5. Use the train dataset to train the ml models.
6. Use the test data to test the model for prediction and accuracy generation

4. SOFTWARE AND HARDWARE REQUIREMENTS

In order to utilize a specific piece of hardware or software, it is essential for a computer or other device to satisfy the system requirements associated with that hardware or software. Table 1 and Table 2 shows the system software and hardware requirements used to execute the project. When a computer is required to interact with a peripheral device, the presence of an I/O port may be necessary. Additionally, certain software may not operate effectively unless it is run on a designated operating system.

It is advisable to verify the system requirements of any software or hardware product prior to making a purchase to confirm its compatibility with your computer. There are options available that feature both low and high system requirements. While the minimum specifications for video games may be adequate, opting for the recommended specifications can enhance overall performance. Upgrading to a more powerful processor and GPU can lead to improvements in graphics and frame rates.

Table 1: System H/W Requirements

S.No	Hardware Configuration	Description
1	Processor	I5 Intel Processor
2	Hard Disk	160GB
3	Monitor	LED, VGA, HDMI, Display Port, USB-C, Low Voltage Differential Signaling (LVDS)
4	Mouse	Two or Three Button Mouse
5	Keyboard	Standard Windows Keyboard
6	RAM	8GB

Table 2: System S/W Requirements

S.No	Software Configuration	Description
1	Operating System	Windows 7/8/10
2	Server Side Script	Python, HTML
3	IDE	PyCharm
4	Libraries Used	Random forest, decision tree, SVM, naive bayes, logistic regression and knn
5	Technology	Pthython 3.6+

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

This research forecasts the occurrence of stroke in patients utilizing classification methodologies. The study highlights the efficacy of classification techniques applied to organized data, such as patient case records, to identify stroke through various parameters and contributing factors. In this study two types of strategies are implemented one is statistical method and other one software based method.

1) Statistical Method: In this study, five statistical variables were employed to assess the effectiveness and utility of the classifiers: accuracy, precision, recall/sensitivity (noting that recall and sensitivity are synonymous in the context of binary classification) and F1 score. Below are the definitions of these statistical parameters [1].

$$Accuracy = \frac{TP+TN}{TP+FP+FN+TN} \quad (1)$$

$$Precision = \frac{TP}{TP+FP} \quad (2)$$

$$Sensitivity = \frac{TP}{TP+FN} \quad (3)$$

$$F1\ Score = \frac{2 \times (recall \times precision)}{(recall + precision)} \quad (4)$$

Where,

TP = true positive

FN = false negative,

FP = false positive

TN =true negative

Random Forest demonstrates superior performance compared to other classifiers, achieving an accuracy of 0.99, as determined by equation (1). This accuracy is the highest among various machine learning algorithms, while the SVM and LR exhibited commendable results within deep learning methodologies. A comparative analysis of the machine learning techniques is presented in Table III, accompanied by a chart in Figure 2 that

illustrates the dominance of the Random Forest method over other machine learning algorithms, utilizing performance metrics derived from equations (1-4). The performance metrics for the ML techniques are detailed in Table 3. Additionally, the comparison between the Random Forest, Decision Tree (DT), and K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN) methods is illustrated in the bar chart in Figure 3. The analysis clearly indicates that the Random Forest algorithm surpasses all Boosting algorithms and deep neural network approaches across all evaluated criteria.

Table 3: Comparison of various Machine Learning Algorithms

Algorithm	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1-score
LR	0.71	0.69	0.73	0.71
DT	0.98	1.0	0.95	0.97
RF	0.99	1.0	0.98	0.99
KNN	0.96	1.0	0.92	0.96
SVM	0.82	0.84	0.77	0.81

Figure 2. Comparison of evaluation metrics of various machine learning algorithms.

2) Software Approach: All of the above mentioned statistical methods test scenarios were successfully executed using software approaches without any difficulties. No issues were identified.

The test results are explained from figures 3 to 5 is as follows:

Figure 3. Illustration of home page

Figure 4. Illustration of Upload dataset

Table 4: Comparison of various Machine Learning Algorithms

Algorithm	Accuracy
LR	0.84
DT	0.96
RF	0.98
KNN	0.91
SVM	0.63
NB	0.90

Figure 5. Comparison of evaluation metrics of various machine learning algorithms.

Random Forest and DT demonstrates superior performance compared to other classifiers, achieving an accuracy of 0.98 and 0.96, as tested and shown in table 4. This accuracy is the highest among various machine learning algorithms, while the SVM and LR exhibited commendable results within deep learning methodologies.

3) Comparative Analysis:

A comparative analysis is carried out of this paper with the two types of methods and results are presented in below figure 6.

Figure 6. Comparative Analysis

6. CONCLUSION

Stroke is a serious medical condition that can be life-threatening and requires immediate intervention to mitigate potential long-term effects. The development of machine learning (ML) and deep learning models may facilitate early detection of strokes, thereby minimizing their severe repercussions. This research evaluates the effectiveness of various machine learning (ML) and boosting algorithms in predicting strokes based on a range of biological indicators. Also, compared the two methods of computing to detection of brain stroke and result shows that RF is the best method to forecast the

brain stroke. The random forest classification method demonstrates superior performance, achieving a classification accuracy of 99%, outperforming the other techniques analyzed. The findings indicate that the random forest approach is more effective than alternative methods in predicting brain strokes when assessed through cross-validation metrics.

Conflict of interest statement

Authors declare that they do not have any conflict of interest.

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